

RTM-Worx Twins for Race-tracking Classification

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Introduction

- **Infusion of a large complex part, aerospace application**
 - Can RTM-Worx handle this?
 - Import geometry, apply properties
- **Trial injections at NCC**
 - Compare simulation with experiment
 - More accurate if we use recorded $p(t)$ at gate
 - Viscosity change during injection, $\eta(t)$
- **Race-tracking**
 - Bridging in corners, channels/low V_f at edges of the part
 - Aluminium inserts: injection at 120 deg.C, cure at 180 deg.C
- **Inversion with ML, training with simulations**
 - Performance, robustness
 - Mesh sensitivity

Infusion – RTM-Worx model

- X-Coarse:
 - 8329 nodes
 - 20790 triangles
 - 36608 tets

■ Left: flow mesh, channels and runners

■ Right: 3D elements

Digital Twin

- Process twin
- Experimental data + simulation model
- Custom boundary condition: $p(t)$ (generate script for simulation)
- Resin arrival times = (pattern) to match
- Model-base process monitoring (2016, ECOMISE project)

Race-tracking

- Left: no race tracking, right: a race tracking case (all gaps < 1 mm)

Setup

- **Input: template model + CSV file (416 cases):**
 - $p(t)$, $\eta(t)$
 - 8 race-tracking sections gap sizes (Hele-Shaw flow)
 - 3 3D sections (V_f , k_{11} , k_{22} , k_{33})
- **Output: Resin arrival times @ sensors (+ dry spots)**
- **NCC machine 014-0734: Dell Precision 7920 (x64-based PC)**
Intel® Xeon® Silver 4110 @ 2.1 GHz, 8 cores, 16 threads
Cache: L1 64 KB/core, L2 1 MB/core, L3 11 MB shared
- **NCC machine 014-2212: Dell Precision 7875 (x64-based PC)**
AMD Ryzen™ Threadripper™ PRO 7965WX @ 4.2-5.3 GHz, 24 cores, 48 threads
Cache: L1 64 KB/core, L2 1 MB/core, L3 128 MB shared
- **SALT script in batch mode, # solver threads = # CPU threads**
(asynchronous tasks, communication via queues for jobs & output)

Speedup – Multithreading

- **Maximum speedup = 100% / #cores**
- **SALT uses M:N scheduler,**
 - M = # OS threads
 - N = # SALT tasks
- **Overhead < 5%**
 - File i/o (results, log)
 - Communication
 - Synchronisation

Implementation Details

- High accuracy on coarse meshes
- Avoid 3D tets with very low volume/edge length ratio
- Combine different elements:
 - 3D tets for reinforcement (if necessary)
 - 2D shell elements: flow media (Darcy), racetracking (Hele-Shaw)
 - 1D line elements: runners, racetracking (Poiseuille), noodle (Darcy)
- Fast flow front tracking algorithm (2022-2024, RTM-Worx 3.11-3.13)
- Multithreading: SALT (send-receive-reply)
- Solver: single core, SIMD accelerated
- Scripted custom $p(t)$ at injection gate, time dependent viscosity

Performance / 15K projection

Mesh	Nodes	Mach/Threads	Wall clock time [min]	Avr. run [sec]	Est. 15K
X-coarse	8361	0734 / 16	118	17	3 days
Coarse	13255	0734 / 16	267	39	1 week
Fine	27142	0734 / 16	1102	159	1 month
X-coarse	8329	2212 / 48	24	3	1 day
Coarse	13209	2212 / 48	57	8	1.5 days
Fine	27040	2212 / 48	232	33	1 week
Ultra-fine	105200	2212 / 48	4562	658	4 months

Results – Mesh sensitivity

- Number of matching cases within AVG +/- 3*STDEV
- Total cases: 416
- U-fine & Fine: 21
- U-fine & Fine & Coarse: 19
- Across all 4 meshes: 12

U-fine mesh matching-cases (Experimental AVG+/-3*STDEV)	Fine mesh matching-cases (Experimental AVG+/-3*STDEV)	Coarse mesh matching-cases (Experimental AVG+/-3*STDEV)	X-coarse mesh matching-cases (Experimental AVG+/-3*STDEV)
2	2	2	2
4	4	4	
15	15	15	
18	18		
24			
36	36	36	36
59	59	59	59
85	85	85	85
89			
93	93	93	
100	100	100	100
103	103		
104	104	104	104
		112	112
129			
158			
170			
174	174	174	174
179	179	179	
183	183	183	183
186	186	186	186
			187
193	193		
203			
222			
279	279	279	279
281			
287			
297	297	297	
329	329	329	329
341	341	341	341
			344
348	348	348	
409	409	409	
31 matching-cases	22 matching-cases	20 matching-cases	15 matching-cases

matching-cases count on mesh group: U-fine, Fine mesh	matching-cases count on mesh group: U-fine, Fine, Coarse mesh	matching-cases count across all 4 mesh files
2	2	2
4	4	
15	15	
18		
36	36	36
59	59	59
85	85	85
93		
100	100	100
103		
104	104	104
174	174	174
179	179	
183	183	183
186	186	186
193		
279	279	279
297	297	
329	329	329
341	341	341
348	348	
409	409	
21 cases	19 cases	12 cases

Conclusions & outlook

- **With relative coarse meshes and a fast solver implementation, we can run many moderately complex 3D models in reasonable time.**
- **Reliability and predictability are important requirements, robust error handling and high-level multithreading algorithms speed up development considerably.**
- **Faster hardware required for complex cases: 3D models with many parameters (Aerospace, Wind energy)**
- **Next steps:**
 - **actually train ML software**
 - **larger part, additional complexity**

Thank you for your attention!

